

**WOMEN'S TOUCH ON SPORTS SCREEN:
EXAMINING THE WOMEN SPORTS PRESENTER
PERCEPTION ON TV FOOTBALL SHOWS**

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Abstract:

Women whose interest in sports and football increase day by day maintain their interest both as active and passive participants (Acosta and Kartepender, 2014). This interest has not been limited merely to watching sports. It has gone so far as women working professionally in the media (Performance Communications, 2016). Thus, it is believed that it will not be wrong to say that the male dominant structure in sports and the sports industry has begun to display differences with the professional participation of women in the sports media (reporter, presenter, author, editor etc.) The power of television is a fact that should be taken into consideration in the developing and changing world. Gender studies on sports media demonstrates that women sports are not taken seriously and does not get the respect it deserves in the media (Cooky, Mesner and Hextrum, 2013). Thus, the place of women in sports programmes and the perception this creates in Turkish society has become an important subject that should be studied. The aim of this study is to find out how female presenters in football programmes are perceived by viewers. For this purpose, the interview technique which is a qualitative research method has been used to get more detailed and in-depth data. The data from the interviews has been analyzed using the content analysis method and coded under appropriate themes. Research results are divided into two as positive and negative thoughts. The thoughts of the participants were evaluated in two categories as 'the perception of women on screen and program content. The findings of the study show that the presence of women in football programmes is generally viewed positively. In addition, it can be said that women on football screen is perceived as 'beneficial', 'necessary' and 'beautiful'.

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1. Introduction

The place of television and its effects on society in the developing and changing world emerges as a reality which should be taken into consideration (Abercrombie, 1996:1-8) Television broadcast developed greatly especially in the late 1990s and most countries had television broadcasting. With this, television entered the lives of people of different classes and watching TV started to be seen as a routine activity of daily life.

The effect of television has not been limited to being a routine watching activity in people's daily lives. It has become social phenomenon about which people talk and in their relationship. Hatley (2008) believes that the thought of erasing television from people's lives is nearly an impossible and utopian approach (Hartley, 2008:1-3). In this respect, the effects of TV broadcasting on viewers and the perception it creates is seen as an important tool in reflecting the features of the era it is shown in.

One of the basic events in which television meets sports and becomes permanent is stated as the live broadcast of American National Baseball League (MLB). The history of television in the 20th century is studied under three headings as 'early engineering', 'creativity' and 'economic era'. The creativity era which marks the beginning of making programmes is seen as the era during which sports firmed its place in television (Schultz, 2002:1).

It is possible to study the television broadcasting process in Turkey in two periods as 'TRT' and 'private channels'. Television broadcasting which was carried out by TRT from one centre for a specific time got a different dimension with the increase in private channels in the 1990s. With private investments, variety in television broadcasting increased and television programs for different social structures became widespread (Çelenk, 2005:13-25). With time, sports became popular in Turkish TV channels along with other fields. TRT, which was criticized about programme content and variety, started setting up different channels. Channel 3 (TRT 3) started to broadcast educational and sports programmes. Following this, the private sector started broadcasting. The channel Star-1 started broadcast on topics which the society had most interest in and started live broadcast of the First Football League. Thus, a new dimension was observed in television broadcasting (Özer, 2004:254-255).

Television has a strong potential in creating products of popular culture, and servicing these to society. Thus, it serves the function of a locomotive. In this respect, the social and emotional bond created among individuals through sports is regarded as one of the most important fields by channels who aim to reach masses and hold their interest (Gitlin, 1986:179-182; Zorlu, 2016).

The process which developed and changed parallel to the development of sports improved the sports- media relationship. The support between media and sports resulted in the industrialisation of different branches of sports. One of the most prominent branches among these industries is football (Katirci, 2012:39). It can be said

that the same situation is valid for Turkey as sports programmes in general have football as their content. A study carried out by the Higher Board of Radio and Television seems to support this statement. According to this study, 81% of those who watch sports programmes in Turkey watch football and related topics (RTÜK, 2008:16).

Although it is said that the male-dominant structure in sports and the sports industry has also been observed in women's presence and professional participation in sports media (reporter, presenter, author, editor etc.) (Özsoy, 2008: 205; Darvin and Sagas, 2017) it can be said that this male-dominant structure has changed at present. The active and passive consumption of sports is seen as an important activity in today's society. Parallel to this, women who have increased interest in sports and football maintain this interest both as active and passive (spectator, viewer or follower) participants (Acosta and Kartepender, 2014). In the U.S.A, 2015 Female Football World Cup finals were watched nearly as much as the NBA finals. FIFA 16, which is one of the most famous digital football games, responded to this interest by having female football in the game. The changes mentioned are not limited to the interest and viewing of female sports. It is also observed as the professional participation of females in the media (Performance Communications, 2016). However, despite the striking increase in the interest and participation of women in the last quarter of the twentieth century, this social change was not sufficiently observed in sports media (Cooky, Mesner and Musta, 2015). It is possible to state that a similar situation is valid for Turkey. Until 2014, sports programmes in both local and national TV channels hosted mostly male presenters, commentators, and guests. Following this year, it is seen that females are more frequently seen in channels such as NTV Sports, A Sports, TRT Sports, Tivibu Sports and Bein Sports in different roles (presenter, commentator, guests etc.) The main issue studied in research on social gender in sports media is the lack of context in women sports and the fact that it is not handled seriously and respectfully (Cooky, Mesner and Hextrum, 2013). In this respect, how women participate in sports programmes and the perception this creates in Turkish society has become an important topic that should be studied. Based on this, the main purpose of this study is the evaluation of the perception female presenters, commentators or guests in football programmes on Turkish TV channels have on viewers based on the thoughts of these viewers.

2. Material and Methods

The interview technique, which is a qualitative method, has been used in this study to obtain more detailed and in-depth data. A semi-structured interview form was created consisting of two questions appropriate for the aim of the study and individual interviews were made (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013:147-167). The research group consists of a total of 16 people who are students at four different departments (Sports Management, Coaching Education, Sports Teaching, and Recreation) at Anadolu University Faculty of Sports Sciences based on volunteerism. There are two male and two female students from each department. The interviews which were carried out in a

place where the students would feel comfortable were recorded. Then they were deciphered and were transcribed into written texts. The data transcribed into written texts were coded and analyzed by three researches using the content analysis method. The main procedure in content analysis was gathering similar data within the framework of specific concepts and themes and interpreting these in a way that the reader can understand. This process is evaluated under four headings:

- 1) the coding of data;
- 2) determining the themes;
- 3) arranging the codes and themes;
- 4) the definition and evaluation of findings (Taylor et al., 2016:161-194).

The reliability of the coding for the analysis has been calculated by using the formula developed by Miles and Huberman (1994). This formula is $\text{Consensus} / (\text{Consensus} + \text{Dissidence}) * 100$ in which there is internal coherence. Positive and negative categories on the perception of women on TV and program content were determined based on the data obtained in the study. These were coded and themes were created. According to this, the reliability coefficient among codes was found to be 0.85 for positive thoughts and 0.90 for negative thoughts. It is stated that the coefficient for reliability for codes in the content analysis should be 0.80 or above (Miles and Huberman, 1994:64; Neeuendorf, 2002:142-143; Patton; 2002). Based on this, it can be said that reliability among codes within the context of the study are in an ideal level.

3. Findings

Eight female and eight male university students participated in this study. The nicknames and the personal team information of the participants and the dates of interview are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Information about participants

Participants	Education	Department	Sex	Interview Date
Bereket	Undergraduate	Coaching Education	Female	25.11.2016
Bilge	Undergraduate	Coaching Education	Female	25.11.2016
Kerem	Undergraduate	Coaching Education	Male	26.11.2016
Rovski	Undergraduate	Coaching Education	Male	27.11.2016
Semiramis	Undergraduate	Sports Teaching	Female	23.11.2016
Kıvırcık	Undergraduate	Sports Teaching	Female	23.11.2016
Centilmen	Undergraduate	Sports Teaching	Male	22.11.2016
Timuçin	Undergraduate	Sports Teaching	Male	22.11.2016
Alize	Undergraduate	Recreation	Female	22.11.2016
Deniz	Undergraduate	Recreation	Female	23.11.2016
Uğur	Undergraduate	Recreation	Male	23.11.2016
Kağan	Undergraduate	Recreation	Male	23.11.2016
Büşra	Undergraduate	Sports Management	Female	22.11.2016
Melisa	Undergraduate	Sports Management	Female	22.11.2016
Faruk	Undergraduate	Sports Management	Male	22.11.2016
Pehlivan	Undergraduate	Sports Management	Male	22.11.2016

*The total interview time of the participants is 101 minutes 61 seconds.

The findings of the study are given in Figure 1 so that they can be better understood and seen as a whole. The findings are divided into two as positive and negative thoughts. Each of the positive and negative thoughts are given in two categories as 'the perception of women on TV' and 'program content'. In the negative thoughts the theme 'sexuality' and 'disharmony' was found under the heading 'program content'. On the other hand, positive thoughts on 'the perception of women on TV' were found as 'equality' and 'beauty'. Positive thoughts for the category of program content was 'quality'.

Figure 1: Themes and Codes towards the Thoughts of the Participants

Explanations and examples on themes and codes are as follows;

I. Negative Thoughts

Category 1. The perception of women on TV

“Sexuality” and “disharmony” were found within the context of negative thoughts on the perception of women on TV.

The coding and sample content for 'sexuality' are as follows:

a. Sexual Object

Pehlivan: “Rather than females, I believe it is sincerer if males comment as they have a football background. I find it repelling when ladies are in sports programmes as they are used as sexual objects. Do I watch them? Yes, I do because I have a habit of watching sports channels.”

Faruk: “Of course it is nicer to see a female instead of a male with a hard voice. And as males in general watch football or sports, it is necessary to do something to attract the males’ attention. If they have female presenters of course they will be more attractive sexually.”

b. Incitement

Melisa: “...I mean ladies are used on screen as sexual objects. When someone not interested in sports watches the programmes, some men just don’t listen and masturbate looking at her.”

The coding and sample content for the theme 'disharmony' are as follows;

c. Artificial

Timuçin: “No matter what she does to adapt herself, it is not enough. I mean they reflect this ’cos they don’t do this in their daily life. I mean I don’t think they get pleasure from football and they’re not there because they really love football.”

d. Repelling

Timuçin: "I cannot get what I want to get from the program. Either I want for her talk to end or I change channels"

Timuçin: "I mean; I don't think that people watch others more. I mean I see it as attracting women to football. And when it's like that, I can't get what I want from the program. Either I wait for her talk to end or change channels."

Category 2. Program content

The theme 'monotony' emerged in the context of negative thoughts on the content of football programmes with female presenters. The coding and sample content on the theme 'monotony' are as follows:

a. Serious and Formal

Pehlivan: "I mean; I find it unattractive. For example, we criticize white football but the warm atmosphere in that can't be found there."

b. They Are Not Competent on the Topic

Bilge: "Of course I have some knowledge but I have no other contact. I don't much find about football commentators. I mean it's not a program that would satisfy me."

Faruk: "They are not competent enough on the topic. We see presenters rather than commentators. A few commentators. I mean they don't know much about the topic. How can I say? I don't care for their comments."

c. They do not feel football in their heart

Timuçin: "I mean they look as if they were placed there later. They cannot get rid of that. I mean they do not feel football in their heart. Well... I think so because everyone there feels football in their heart. I mean it looks out of place because they do not feel it. I mean no matter how hard she tries to get adapted, it does not work."

Pehlivan: "Sometimes I get distracted from football. I mean when I see a female presenter arguing with Ümit Özat, I think that Ümit Özat is right. Why because as women did not have a place in football before this, I got the perception that they won't have that place in the future. I mean I'm following that perception."

II. Positive Thoughts

Category 1. The Perception of women on screen

The themes 'Equality' and 'Beauty' were created within the context of positive thoughts on the perception of women on screen.

The coding and sample content for the equality theme are as follows:

a. Gives Hope

Bereket: "They don't come to that level right after birth. When females succeed in this way, this gives us hope too."

b. Makes us proud

Bereket: "One gets proud I mean because we can see how valuable we are and how we can progress. There are so many murders in our country. Women see themselves as discriminated in

such a society. I mean such things give us hope and courage. The right to speak gives us extra courage."

Semiramis: *"I mean let me put it this way: it makes one proud. I mean you say so women can be at the forefront in Turkey. You know football is seen as a men's game but it seems that this is not so. This helps in getting rid of taboos."*

c. Social Consciousness

Semiramis: *"I mean seeing women in sports programmes or football programmes is quite good. It makes one feel good. I mean, this is my point of view. You know, maybe men may not think so. I mean I'm into sports as a football player I mean I'm speaking for Turkey. This means some things are getting popular and some things are improving in Turkey. Because football is never sex discrimination. I believe that this is very good. I want it to increase. Godwilling it will be better in the future."*

Centilmen: *"Because I think in this way as a Fenerbahçe Fan. In one match, our stadium was filled with females. This was headline news in the world. Nothing bad happened then. Everyone had fun, they supported their team. I believe that women's interest in sports is always an advantage for our society. I mean I see it that way. I see it from that point of view. I mean people might have different views but I see it that way."*

Kıvrıcık: *"It's nice to see female presenters in football why nice because in general Turkish people are really interested in football. Similarly, this is also reflected in things at home. I mean the man comes from work and watches matches all the time his wife doesn't want it so there are problems and arguments at home. Well, this affects everything such as the relationship between couples. I mean it's nice to see women visually either on TV or live programmes I mean it's a good thing. I mean it approves of women like you may also watch this we can also talk about this. It's not just about men. I mean that kind of stuff."*

d. Social Power

Uğur: *"I look at it like this on this topic. I see it in terms of equality, female-male equality. In my personal opinion, this should be more frequent. I mean we shouldn't regard football just as a male game. Females can also comment on it. I mean I think so."*

Bereket: *"If we're talking about equality there must be equality in everything. If men are aware of something and if this right is given to them, females can also do what they want freely."*

Deniz: *"For example I learn many things for example some things I mean I can also comment on things I mean with the opposite sex. I mean they can do it. If I can also do it I mean I feel equal with the opposite sex or that I feel I'm more."*

Kaan: *"They should work in different fields and I think it has a positive effect in this way. It shows to women that they can do everything. I believe that it's good in this respect too."*

e. Social Future

Melisa: *"Let me say it this way then. I remember my childhood now. When there was a Galatasaray-Fenerbahçe game, my dad used to come home immediately. My mum for example wanted to watch a soap opera and they couldn't agree on what to watch and used to have an argument I mean if you think of family matters this could soften that negative atmosphere because as I said when those women someone like themselves, they take her as a role model and a*

sentence of her could be about something in other one's life. It could be a factor which could prevent conflict in families."

Melisa: "It could be useful for society in that way maybe. It could be a triggering factor for housewives. Because you see it on TV. It could make you say if she does it, then I can too."

Büşra: "I have positive thoughts. If women show their presence in different areas in a group where males are dominant I think this is positive. I mean I like that. This could be a new employment area for females."

Bilge: "Our society or people in general have prejudices, I mean what can you do with negative thoughts, how far can you go? When they sit and watch that or if there's an attractive person a young person I mean a young girl playing football and the father says stay home or study, we see that. I started when I was 9. Since I was 9 my father even said let's make you a professional let's get a licence for you. I mean they will become professionals. The girl won't play football in the street. She will play professionally in a club. I mean when it goes down to the beginning it's useful. I mean I think it will have a great contribution. Actually it should have started much earlier."

Bereket: "I'm proud I mean and I see that I'll get a good job in the future. I'm hopeful."

The coding and sample content for the theme beauty are as follows:

f. Satisfaction

Bilge: "First of all, it's a pleasing situation. Now we can see female presenters on NTV of course it's a good thing."

Roovski: "I mean I believe that actually it's a good thing. I mean someone who is not a football player is a commentator in a programme and expresses her views freely."

Centilmen: "First of all, the interest it gives me it increases my interest in sports because it is good for me to see people's increasing interest in sports and its effect on females. Because it's not just for one sex. I mean seeing females' increasing interest in sports is a good thing for society."

Deniz: "I mean it's a good thing for females to prove that they have knowledge in that field. I would also like to see them like that I believe there should be more of that."

Alize: "Because of that I mean it makes me think that I also understand sports, games, football and such stuff when I see females in programmes."

g. Visual Beauty

Kerem: "It looks nice. I mean when it's a women presenting something it is better visually I mean it's nicer to watch that. Also, when you see a female on the channel, it makes you curious. When a football presenter is a female, I feel the programme is worth watching more."

Roovski: "Burcu Esmersoy for example. I mean she is not of football origin but when I watch that is when she comments on football it's different. Seeing a female in that programme, a bit distant to general viewers, a different standard. I believe it's nice visually."

Alize: "I mean generally in commercials etc. when we see females it's more well attractive yes and that makes you stick to the screen. Males, well they are kind of rude and tough. I mean having men in football programmes affects men more but seeing females affects me more as a female viewer."

Kaan: "Seeing female presenters in football I think is nice. Females usually add beauty to wherever they go. In addition, they make the programme more worth viewing and this is good of

course for viewers. And they choose beautiful women and this has a positive effect on viewers. Because most people care for physical appearance, including myself."

Category 2. Programme Content

The theme quality was created under the category programme content. The coding and sample content for the theme quality are as follows;

a. Topic Competence

Kerem: *"I mean there are jokes and such but they never drift away from the main topic. But when it's all males they talk about everything other than football 'cos they say we know about football anyway. Some females are more competent on the topic compared to males."*

Semiramis: *"For example, I mean males, how can I say don't speak orderly and they speak in a rude way but when there's a female present they are more careful. I mean the programme goes on as it should be. They don't get distracted."*

b. Objectivity

Roovski: *"I mean I think actually it's a good thing. Someone not related to football comments on it and expresses her views freely. For example, they are objective towards their team. For example, at present many football players play football and then become commentators and presenters. This is a cliché. When they have male talk there's more slang in it, there are more arguments. There's no objectivity. They support one side usually."*

Centilmen: *"I mean because females are more objective about this. For example, a female fan of Fenerbahçe can watch a game with a female fan of Galatasary but in our society, it is impossible for men to do that. So I think females are better than us about this."*

c. Higher Quality and Serious

Roovski: *"Well a bit higher quality of course. Because there's a female present and they're careful when they speak. Maybe the guest is unable to express all of his/her views but I haven't seen much about that."*

Semiramis: *"Women are better organized than men I mean both in the way they dress and physically also the way they speak more organised. I mean they express what they want to say more formally."*

Uğur: *"Well, in most programmes males were at the forefront previously. In the last 2 or 3 years, women have also been at the forefront. I can comment on it like this. We watch some programmes everyone watches them arguments all the time. When there's female presenters this changes. People act more respectfully."*

Deniz: *"Well, let me put it this way, when we look at men, I mean they are kind of rude gestures and talk. I mean females could be better in that way. I mean to show that it's just sports."*

d. Knowledge / Research

Kaan: *"Some programme guests don't treat them as human beings. I mean this is a general problem in our society. They think the women don't have enough knowledge on the topic. The channel knows this and I guess they test whether the women are competent enough or they train them and then they have them present the programme. I think that they do that because it wouldn't be possible to find such competent female presenters."*

Faruk: *"This is related to a prejudice in society. They go like 'Do you know what offside is?' It's not a bag brand. Maybe they are more competent than most men."*

Centilmen: *"I mean as an example for that I watch Banu Yelkovan and Bağış Erten's programme on NTV Sports. I mean they give incredible information in that programme. They have various videos, they taught me really nice things."*

Semiramis: *"I mean they describe it in a more detailed way. I mean I think they do more research to have different thoughts and more clear thoughts."*

Kerem: *"There were some female presenters that I watched I mean there are some women who know more than men. Thus, if they're doing their job, if they love their job if they are where they are with their own effort then I think they are quite successful."*

4. Results and Discussions

Within the light of the data obtained in the study, positive and negative categories on the perception of women on screen and program content were found out. These were coded to create themes. Based on these, negative thoughts on the perception of women on screen were gathered under the heading 'sexuality' and 'disharmony'. Negative thoughts on program content were gathered under the theme 'monotony'. Positive thoughts on the perception of women on screen were studied under the themes 'equality' and 'beauty' whereas the positive thoughts on programme content were studied under the theme 'quality'. 18.75% (3) of those participating in the study stated negative thoughts on the presence of women on screen. 81.25% (15) of the participants stated that they were pleased about seeing women in sports programmes.

When the themes and codes created using the negative thoughts were studied, it was seen that women in sports programmes were perceived as sexual objects and incitement under the theme 'sexuality'. Perceiving female sports presenters as sexual objects is not a situation observed only in Turkey. It is seen that a newspaper study in the United States stating the thoughts of twenty-three males about female sports commentators revealed thoughts that humiliated women. In addition, the statements such as "I take women more seriously than men because women have breasts" which were found in this study support the view that women are seen as sexual objects (Jensen, 2015). Another example on seeing women in sports programmes is from Canada. Naked news, in other words 'the program with nothing to hide' is a practice that is based on women presenting sports and other types of programmes completely naked (Knight, 2012). Von der Lippe (2002) stated in his study on media, sports, gender and national identity that the image and perception of women in the media are an important factor in the development of national identity. In addition, they made suggestions on keeping in mind cultural differences and similarities when determining how women will be seen in media about sports. In this context, when the examples in the U.S.A, Canada and Turkey are evaluated, it can be said that perceiving women in sports programmes as sexual objects results from the perception of individuals rather than practice.

Participants who stated negative thoughts generally said that women do not fit into football. In this context, the thought that women presenters are 'repelling' and 'artificial' under the theme 'disharmony' is the dominant thought.

There are some studies in literature that support this view. The newspaper *Hurriyet* made a questionnaire among 3504 readers and asked the question: "what do you think of women being football commentators?" 1860 (53.1%) of the participants responded by saying "It is wrong and very unnecessary" (hurriyet.com.tr, 2012). In addition, there are studies questioning whether being a sports commentator and presenting sports news is suitable for women as well as studies aiming to find out the difficulties that these women experience. In a study by Strong (2007) female sports reporters and writers stated that they feel sufficient professionally but said that the negative thoughts towards them affected their motivation and that they had a reaction against this (Strong, 2007:7-18).

Within the context of negative thoughts under the category programme content in the theme monotony the thoughts on female football presenters were found as 'serious and formal', 'they are not competent on the subject' and 'they do not feel football' within the context of negative thoughts under the category programme content in the theme monotony. In more simple terms, the participants who had negative thoughts see female presenters in sports programmes as insufficient. Although only 18,75% of the participants in the study think in this way, there are some results in the literature that support this view. In a study in which the experiences of female sports reporters were evaluated, female reporters were asked to write such as "which football player is more handsome", "who has more beautiful legs", "I did not understand off-side" and someone among the spectators said to a female presenter: "you should go home and do housework" These statements support the negative thoughts against female presenters (Özsoy, 2008:209). Ward (2004) states that sports is one of the fields in which sexist sayings are widely seen. In a study aiming to find the perceptions of 423 participants about football programmes, the statements "males commentators comment on football better than females" had an average of 3.13 whereas the statement "female commentators make good comments on football" had an average of 2.46. This study shows parallelism to the negative perception and thoughts towards female football presenters concerning program content (Özsoy, 2014:269). In addition to all these, in a football programme on a national Turkish TV channel, something that could be an example for negative thoughts happened. Ex national player Ümit Özat had an argument with a female football commentator during a live broadcast and said "I will not talk about football with a woman." He then left the studio (haberturk.com, 2012). This event could be shown as a negative example towards the perception of women on TV.

In the study, it was found out that the positive thoughts about female sports presenters were higher in contrast to the ones present in literature. Within the context of positive thoughts the themes 'equality' and 'beauty' were found for the category of the perception of women on screen. The concept 'hopeful', 'makes us proud', 'social

consciousness', 'social power' and 'social future' were found under the theme equality. To put it in other words, female football presenters create a perception of equality among viewers and viewers think that the female is getting stronger individually and socially in Turkish society and that this will have a positive effect on other females as well. Raisborough and Bhatti (2007) emphasize the development of women in society with the statement 'the power of women' and say that this plays an important role in creating new opportunities and identity for women. Similarly, Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) stated that the power of women increases equally with the increase in free time activity and participation in sports and this in a way is a challenge against man hegemony. It can be said that the positive thoughts found in the study also have similar characteristics. In addition, television has the power to affect people (Whannel, 1995:141-191), women have an important place in society (Kew, 2003:124-126) and football is the most popular sports in the world. (Koller and Brandle, 2015) when these facts are taken into consideration, it can be said that the trio 'television, women and football' are quite powerful and that the thoughts of the participants could be evaluated with this point of view. Television and media have the role of emphasizing the inequality between females and males and giving a social message to society. Seeing females in television programmes is important. However, the representation and place of women on screen does not yet get the value it deserves and remains insufficient. (Dündar, 2010: 95-104)

The theme 'beauty' emerged as the participants frequently mentioned the concept beauty on the perception of women on screen. The theme 'beauty' has been evaluated in two groups as 'satisfaction' and 'visual beauty' what is desired to be put forward in the satisfaction statement is that seeing women on screen is beautiful, in other words satisfactory. However, it is possible to evaluate this situation in a different way. Since the past, the beauty and body of women have been one of the elements that have faced massive intervention (Canatan, 2015:54). Lavoie (2013:46) argues that practices thinking that "sex sells" related to women being present in sports and on the screen are harmful and might lead to a negative reaction. In this case, the quality and content of possible programmes are important. Thus, when the 'naked news' in Canada or the events in football programs in Italy with females in them (youtube.com) are taken into consideration, it can be argued that football programmes in Turkey with female presenters are suitable for professional broadcasting rules and ethics as well as being high quality.

Participants who argue that female presenters add beauty to football programmes also say that female presenters add quality to the content of football programmes. In this context, the codes 'topic competence', 'objectivity', 'higher quality and serious', 'knowledgeable/research' were found under the theme 'quality' in the program content category. Schoch (2013) has stated that female reporters have a more humane view and that they have a softer approach to technical analysis and phenomenon developed by males. In addition, the fact that female football presenters are perceived as 'objective' could be related to the fact that males are usually ex

footballers or club managers and that this is reflected in their thoughts and comments. In their study, Ünsal and Ramazanoğlu (2013:42) asked the question “Do you think that the sports media has objective programmes?” to the participants. The fact that 69.14% of the participants responded with 'no' might be considered as similar to this thought. In this context, it can be said that the perception of objectivity is lower in programmes in which males are dominant and higher in programmes with female presenters. That female presenters are 'higher quality and serious' is among the thoughts of the participants. A recent study shows that there is slang, swearing and violence in football programmes (Özsoy, 2014:296). However, it can be said that football programmes with females have the minimum amount or none of these negative elements.

To sum up, based on the data of the study the perception on female football presenters are generally positive among the participants. In Turkey, females experience problems in social life and work life and are generally in the background. In addition, social gender perception is far from 'equality' in Turkey (Research Center for Social Gender and Female Studies, 2016:5-29) when these are taken into consideration, it can be said that having female presenters in football programmes will result in important changes society in terms of the place and role of women in society. Hardin (2013) stated that the change desired in the context about the concepts female, media and sports is related to the change of those who are decision makers. Similarly, he states that another step in doing this is increasing the number of women in the sports media. In this context, the positive results of the study may be stated as important results that should be taken into consideration and furth.

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